
An Evaluation of the Implementation of Gap Bridging in the Job Rotation Policy at Zamtel, Lusaka, Zambia: A Framework for Enhancing Operationalisation

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to develop a structured framework for enhancing the operationalization of the job rotation policy at Zamtel, a telecommunications company based in Lusaka, Zambia. The specific objectives were firstly, to examine the job rotation provisions embedded in Zamtel's Human Resource policy, secondly, to assess the job rotation activities implemented across departments, and thirdly, to evaluate the applicability of the Theory of Constraints to Zamtel's job rotation strategy. The study adopted a qualitative research approach grounded in the interpretivist paradigm and employed a phenomenological research design to capture employees lived experiences and perceptions. A purposive sampling technique was used to select fifteen (15) participants comprising Human Resource personnel and departmental heads. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews and document analysis and analysed using thematic content analysis guided by the study objectives and the Theory of Constraints framework. The findings revealed that although job rotation is formally recognised within Zamtel's Human Resource policy, its implementation is inconsistent across departments. While some administrative units applied job rotation practices, specialised departments exhibited limited participation. Planned job rotation activities such as structured onboarding, cross-functional attachments, and mentorship programmes were found to be irregular and weakly coordinated. The study further identified key constraints affecting effective operationalization, including limited budgetary support, low employee readiness, and resistance linked to career progression concerns. The study concludes that job rotation at Zamtel has the potential to support employee development and retention but is undermined by structural and resource-based constraints. It recommends the adoption of a standardized job rotation framework, improved budget allocation, and enhanced communication to support uniform implementation across departments. Future research is recommended to examine employee perceptions in greater depth and to benchmark best practices from comparable organisations.

KEYWORDS: Job Rotation, Operationalization, Job Rotation Policy, Policy, Policy Framework

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1. INTRODUCTION

Organizations in the 21st century face rapid changes in the external business environment that impact the operation of the internal environment (Blanchard, 2006). The demands made by customers, skilled workers, regulators, social activists and shareholders increase the pressure on firms to deliver excellent performance while satisfying the diverse needs of stakeholders (Schermerhorn, et al., 2004; Watson, 2007;). An understanding of job rotation is necessary to decipher the needs of the individuals and groups within the organization to utilize maximize experience which translates to high performance workplace. High performance workplace strives to get the best in people as a means to achieve sustainable results. Leaders, who put people first when setting the organizational objectives, inspire their workforce to pursue high performance while meeting the expectations of all the stakeholders (McClelland & Burnham, 2003).

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In today's fast-paced and continuously growing business environment there is a high demand for energy, creativity and innovation. Employees are constantly seeking new experiences, opportunities that can develop their skills. Job rotation is a modern human resources approach where employees shift amongst different roles within the organization (Blanchard, 2006).

What is important for human resource development is that the enhancement of human resources not only is reached through technical and specialized training, but also the development of personnel's training in different ways, and this method will not be successful without implementing strategic plans in the field of human resource management (Rose et al., 2011; Saravani and Abbasi, 2013). The job rotation system, which saves time, costs and better performance is one of the two role mechanisms that both eases the organization's managerial affairs and leads to the development of human resources (Redditt et al., 2019). Also, it cultivates human resources in various dimensions. Job rotation is a method used to turn members who are partial and limited to into holistic individuals that see and understand problems on a larger scale. It is a process that employees of an organization at different levels of the family, work in a shift manner (Porter and Steers, 2013). Job rotation means replacing duties between persons or employees for increasing motivation and enthusiasm in their workplace. In organizations, the director of the organization assigns different duties and responsibilities to the members in different time periods and in proportion to the activities and programs of the organization, in order to provide a ground for the person to get acquainted with other activities and discover their talents and skills (Nafei, 2014).

In the twenty-first century, organizations are confronted with swift changes in the external environment, which affect their internal operation (Harvey et al., 2013). For instance, stakeholders, including customers, skilled workers, regulators, social activists, and shareholders, increasingly pressure businesses to achieve exceptional results while meeting their diverse needs (Nyuur et al., 2016). Scholars (e.g., Akhbari and Zargarani, 2011; Mohsan et al., 2012) have long recognized that job rotation is an effective strategy for achieving compelling performances in organizations. According to Mohsan et al. (2012), having a mechanism like job rotation to affect employees' performance and improve their commitment to their work is one way to increase employee motivation. As a result, it is suggested that job rotation is not only a desirable but also an unavoidable need (Sanséau & Opoku, 2019), as it is seen as a promising method for organizations to develop their employees, managers, and executives holistically (Mohsan et al., 2012).

Zamtel has been confronted with swift changes in the external and internal environments which have affected its internal operation. According to (Zamtel, 2021), the Retention policy indicates that Job rotation provides an opportunity for employees to improve their skills and broaden their experience. Secondment or attachment opportunities in Zamtel are offered to promote the personal and professional development of employees while meeting the service needs of the company (Zamtel, 2021).

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The telecommunications industry is characterised by rapid technological advancement, continuous digital transformation, and increasing convergence of services, all of which demand sustained workforce reskilling and organisational flexibility. Global evidence suggests that between 30% and 50% of technical skills in information and telecommunications sectors become obsolete within three to five years, necessitating structured internal learning and employee mobility mechanisms such as job rotation (World Economic Forum, 2020; OECD, 2021). Job rotation is therefore widely recognised as a strategic human resource management practice for enhancing skills diversification, employee adaptability, and long-term organisational performance (Campion et al., 1994; Ortega, 2001).

In Zambia, the telecommunications sector operates within a highly regulated and competitive environment overseen by the Zambia Information and Communications Technology Authority (ZICTA). According to ZICTA sector performance reports, mobile network operators face persistent challenges related to service quality, network expansion, and skills availability, particularly in technically specialised functions (ZICTA, 2022). These pressures are intensified for state-owned enterprises, which must simultaneously meet commercial performance targets and public service obligations (World Bank, 2021).

Zambia Telecommunications Company Limited (Zamtel), as Zambia's state-owned telecommunications provider, employs a workforce comprising both administrative and highly specialised technical personnel. Zamtel's Annual Reports and Corporate Strategic Plans consistently emphasise human capital development, internal capacity building, and talent retention as critical enablers of operational efficiency and service delivery (Zamtel, 2020; Zamtel, 2022). As part of this strategic intent, job rotation is formally embedded within Zamtel's Human Resource and retention policy to facilitate skills transfer, employee development, and succession planning.

However, despite the existence of this policy framework, evidence from internal organisational practices and management disclosure indicates that the operationalisation of job rotation at Zamtel remains uneven and inconsistent across departments. Zamtel (2022) acknowledges challenges related to skills concentration in specialised technical roles, limited internal mobility, and the need for enhanced workforce versatility to support network modernisation and digital service expansion. These challenges mirror findings from studies of job rotation in technically specialised organisations, where policy adoption does not necessarily translate into effective implementation due to structural rigidity, skills specificity, and resource constraints (Ho et al., 2009; Khan, 2018).

The consequences of weak operationalisation of job rotation at Zamtel include continued reliance on narrowly specialised employees, limited cross-functional exposure, constrained leadership development pipelines, and vulnerability to skills gaps during

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staff exits or redeployments. From a human resource management perspective, such outcomes undermine employee engagement and retention, particularly in a sector where competition for skilled telecommunications professionals remains high (ILO, 2022). From an organisational standpoint, ineffective utilisation of internal talent threatens operational resilience and increases dependence on external recruitment and training, which carries significant cost implications for a state-owned enterprise.

Despite these observable challenges, there is a paucity of empirical research examining how and why job rotation policies fail at the operational level within Zambian telecommunications firms, and Zamtel in particular. Existing studies on job rotation within African contexts are largely generic and outcome-focused, with limited attention to organisation-specific implementation constraints and minimal application of constraint-based theoretical frameworks (Adjei et al., 2016; Oparanma & Nwaeke, 2015). Consequently, there is insufficient empirical guidance to inform practical interventions tailored to Zamtel's operational and institutional context. This study therefore addresses a critical empirical and practical gap by analysing the organisational, structural, and resource-based constraints affecting the operationalisation of the job rotation policy at Zamtel. By developing a context-specific operational framework grounded in empirical evidence and the Theory of Constraints, the study seeks to bridge the gap between policy intent and effective implementation, thereby strengthening employee development, internal mobility, and sustainable organisational performance at Zamtel.

1.2 Theoretical Review

The study adopts Human Capital and Theory of Constraints to Evaluate The Implementation Of Gap Bridging In The Job Rotation Policy At Zamtel, Lusaka, Zambia: A Framework For Enhancing Operationalisation

2.4.1 Human Capital Theory

Human Capital Theory was formally advanced by Gary Becker (1964, 1993), building on earlier work by Theodore Schultz (1961). The theory emerged from labour economics and argued that investment in education, training, and work experience enhances employees' productivity and contributes to organisational and national economic growth. Becker distinguished between general human capital, which is transferable across organisations, and firm-specific human capital, which yields greater returns when employees remain within the organisations.

In contemporary human resource management literature, Human Capital Theory has been extended to explain why organisations invest in structured employee development mechanisms such as job rotation. Recent studies argue that job rotation enhances both general and firm-specific human capital by broadening employee skill sets, improving problem-solving ability, and fostering organisational learning (Crook et al., 2019; Minbaeva, 2021). In dynamic industries such as telecommunications, where skills rapidly become obsolete, internal development mechanisms are viewed as more sustainable than continuous external recruitment (World Economic Forum, 2020).

Applied to this study, Human Capital Theory provides the rationale for job rotation as a strategic investment rather than an administrative exercise. At Zamtel, job rotation is intended to enhance employee capability, improve workforce adaptability, and support succession planning. However, the theory also implies that inadequate implementation of development initiatives undermines returns on human capital investment, making effective operationalisation critical.

2.4.2 Theory of Constraints (TOC)

The Theory of Constraints was developed by Eliyahu M. Goldratt in the 1980s and popularised through *The Goal* (Goldratt & Cox, 1984; 2016). TOC originated in operations and production management and is based on the premise that organisational performance is limited by a small number of critical constraints or bottlenecks. According to TOC, improvement efforts should focus on identifying the primary constraint, exploiting it, subordinating other processes to it, elevating the constraint, and repeating the cycle once the constraint shifts.

Over time, TOC has been extended beyond manufacturing to service organisations, public institutions, and human resource systems. Recent applications show that organisational policies, skills shortages, budget limitations, and behavioural resistance can function as systemic constraints that prevent effective strategy execution (Mabin & Balderstone, 2020; Detert et al., 2020).

In the context of job rotation, TOC is particularly useful in explaining why organisations adopt rotation policies but fail to implement them consistently. Constraints such as specialised skill dependency, workload pressures, limited training resources, and employee resistance can restrict the "flow" of learning and skills transfer across departments. This theory therefore underpins Objective 3 of the study by providing a structured lens for analysing constraints affecting the operationalisation of job rotation at Zamtel.

1.3 Conceptual Framework

To effectively examine the implementation of the job rotation policy from the perspective of policy implementers, the study adopted a conceptual framework that integrated subjective and structural experiences. It was designed to express the dual dimensions influencing policy implantation that is the constraints that exist in a system and the phenomenological narratives.

By linking the two components, the conceptual framework provided a frame for understanding the practical limitations of challenges faced by implementors. Bottlenecks in the System as Lived by Policy Implementers and Phenomenological Narrations of Policy

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Implementers on the State of Job Rotations. The first component outlines several challenges that policy implementers face concerning the job rotation policy. Budget constraints can significantly hinder effective implementation, limiting the scope and frequency of rotations that can be offered. Additionally, the quality of staff available to execute the job rotation policy plays a crucial role; if implementers lack necessary skills or experience, it can lead to inefficiency and frustration. Furthermore, the availability of personnel for rotation is vital; insufficient staff can disrupt operations and hinder the achievement of organizational goals. Lastly, the attitudes of staff towards job rotation can greatly influence the policy's success. Positive or negative perceptions can affect participation levels and enthusiasm regarding development opportunities.

The second component focuses on the subjective experiences and insights of policy implementers regarding the state of job rotations. The phenomenological narratives provide a deeper understanding of how the listed bottlenecks manifest in daily work routines and influence the overall effectiveness of the job rotation policy. The experiences shared by policy implementers can reveal how these challenges directly impact their implementation processes. By articulating their feelings and observations, they highlight the emotional and practical implications of the difficulties faced, thereby informing strategy formulation for overcoming them.

The relationship between these components involves several dynamics. The bottlenecks serve as variables that directly affect the narratives of policy implementers, meaning that budget limitations, staff quality, and available personnel are recurring themes in their accounts. Additionally, the qualitative insights derived from the phenomenological narratives enrich the understanding of the quantitative challenges represented by the bottlenecks. This creates a feedback loop in which personal experiences may shed light on previously unrecognized bottlenecks or inspire new strategies for addressing existing challenges. The framework emphasizes the interconnectedness of operational challenges and the subjective experiences of those implementing the policy, suggesting that effectively addressing identified bottlenecks will require a deep understanding of the lived experiences of policy implementers. This holistic perspective can be invaluable for refining and enhancing the job rotation policy

Figure 1: Conceptual framework Independent Dependent

Source: The Author.2025

Figure 1. The conceptual framework for the implementation of gap bridging in the job rotation policy at Zamtel, Lusaka, Zambia: a framework for enhancing operationalisation. (Source: Author's compilation)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Job rotation serves multiple objectives within organizations, addressing challenges such as employee motivation, skill enhancement, and career satisfaction (Kumar & Singh, 2020). By exposing employees to a variety of roles, organizations can create enriched work environments that encourage professional growth and foster job satisfaction. As an inducement to combat resignation, job rotation can enhance employees' understanding of the organization, thereby enhancing their commitment (Gurley, 2021). Implementing a robust job rotation program could help Zamtel retain essential talent and decrease overall turnover rates.

Despite the strategic vision embedded in Zamtel's Retention Policy, several gaps exist regarding the implementation of the Job Rotation Strategy. Firstly, the policy fails to outline specific activities or scenarios for job rotation, leaving employees and management without clear guidance on how these changes will be operationalized (Zamtel, 2021; Chibale & Kaunda, 2019). This lack of actionable steps could lead to confusion and skepticism among employees. Secondly, a structured monitoring and evaluation mechanism is essential to assess the outcomes of job rotations and their effectiveness in improving employee retention. Establishing defined metrics and conducting regular evaluations would enable Zamtel to adapt the strategy as needed (Kumar & Singh, 2020). Lastly, effective communication and training are crucial for the success of job rotation. Zamtel must ensure employees understand the benefits and processes associated with job rotation and provide training for management to ensure smooth implementation (Braun et al., 2019).

Zamtel's Retention Policy, including its Job Rotation Strategy, represents a significant effort to enhance employee retention and improve organizational performance. However, without a clear implementation plan to translate strategy into actionable steps, the

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potential benefits may remain unrealized. Addressing the identified gaps especially in communication, monitoring, and training will be vital for Zamtel to fully leverage job rotation as a retention tool. Moving forward, continued research and organizational focus must aim to rectify these gaps, ensuring that the Retention Policy leads to meaningful enhancements in employee satisfaction and retention rates.

2.2 Benefits of Job Rotation as a Strategic Human Resource Practice

When job rotation is carefully planned, formally structured, and strategically aligned with organisational goals, it delivers a wide range of employee and organisational benefits, particularly in dynamic and skills-intensive industries. Contemporary human resource management literature views job rotation not merely as a staffing mechanism, but as a deliberate learning and performance-enhancement strategy that enables organisations to adapt to internal and external environmental changes (Khan et al., 2021; Kampkötter et al., 2018).

From a learning and systems perspective, job rotation contributes to organisational adaptability by disrupting routine work patterns and stimulating continuous learning. Recent organisational learning studies argue that performance improvement and learning processes interact to reshape organisational behaviour, enabling employees and systems to respond more effectively to change (Minbaeva, 2021). Job rotation facilitates this process by exposing employees to diverse roles, contexts, and problem-solving situations, thereby strengthening both individual and collective learning capacity.

Empirical evidence from financial, manufacturing, and service sectors demonstrates that organisations that implement structured job rotation programmes experience improved employee productivity, knowledge integration, and development of intellectual capital (Crook et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2021). These outcomes support the view that job rotation enhances organisational capability by developing multi-skilled employees who can cope with technological change, market uncertainty, and evolving job demands.

Job rotation has also been shown to contribute positively to employee well-being and motivation. Recent studies indicate that rotating employees across tasks reduces job monotony, prevents boredom, and improves psychological engagement, particularly in roles characterised by repetitive or narrowly defined tasks (Dechawatanapaisal, 2018; Nyathi & Kekwaletswe, 2022). Boredom and disengagement have been empirically linked to absenteeism, turnover intentions, and declining service quality; thus, job rotation serves as a proactive mechanism for sustaining employee motivation and morale (Shantz et al., 2016).

In addition to motivational benefits, job rotation is increasingly recognised as a viable intervention for managing work-related stress and fatigue. Studies conducted in physically demanding and cognitively intensive work environments show that job rotation reduces exposure to repetitive strain, mental exhaustion, and task overload by varying physical and cognitive demands across roles (Serrano et al., 2016; Padula et al., 2017). Where job rotation is implemented alongside ergonomic and workload planning, organisations report reductions in work-related injuries, stress levels, and absenteeism (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, 2019).

From a talent management and succession planning perspective, job rotation plays a critical role in identifying high-potential employees and preparing them for future leadership roles. Contemporary leadership development literature argues that cross-functional exposure enables employees to develop broader organisational understanding, strategic thinking, and decision-making competence (Bono et al., 2021). By rotating employees through diverse functions, organisations are better able to assess latent capabilities, align talent with organisational needs, and create internal pipelines for key positions, thereby enhancing business continuity.

Job rotation also supports functional flexibility and multiskilling, which are essential in today's knowledge-driven and resource-constrained organisations. Recent studies highlight that employees who acquire multiple competencies through rotation become more valuable organisational assets, capable of performing a wider range of tasks and responding quickly to operational disruptions (Minbaeva, 2021; Kampkötter et al., 2018). This flexibility reduces dependence on narrowly specialised roles and enhances workforce resilience.

Furthermore, job rotation contributes to employee retention and organisational commitment when it is perceived as fair, developmental, and aligned with career progression. Evidence shows that employees are more likely to remain with organisations that invest in their growth, provide learning opportunities, and support internal mobility (Shantz et al., 2016; Nyathi & Kekwaletswe, 2022). Given the high costs associated with replacing skilled employees, particularly in technical industries, job rotation represents a cost-effective retention strategy.

Finally, in industries characterised by rapid technological change, such as telecommunications, job rotation enables organisations to optimise employee skills and ensure better role fit. By systematically exposing employees to different functions, organisations can match individual strengths to organisational needs, improve deployment decisions, and minimise skill mismatches (Chen et al., 2020). When employees exit the organisation, internal successors who have rotated across roles can assume responsibilities with minimal disruption, thereby safeguarding operational continuity (Bono et al., 2021).

Contemporary literature affirms that job rotation when strategically designed and effectively operationalised enhances employee learning, motivation, health, flexibility, and career development, while simultaneously strengthening organisational capability,

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resilience, and performance. These benefits provide a strong justification for examining how job rotation policies are operationalised within organisations such as Zamtel.

2.3 Extent and Nature of Job Rotation Practices Implemented Across Departments

2.3.1 Global Empirical Evidence

Globally, empirical studies demonstrate that job rotation is increasingly embedded within formal HR policy frameworks as part of integrated talent management and leadership development strategies. Biemann and Weckmüller (2019) found that organisations with clearly articulated job rotation policies specifying eligibility, duration, learning outcomes, and career progression pathways reported higher levels of employee engagement and internal mobility. Their study emphasised that policy clarity reduces perceptions of favouritism and enhances employee acceptance of rotation initiatives.

Similarly, Kampkötter et al. (2018), in a large-scale European study, demonstrated that job rotation policies positively influence performance only when embedded within coherent HR systems. Where policies lacked operational guidance, job rotation was inconsistently applied and failed to produce sustained performance gains. These findings highlight the importance of policy design as a foundation for effective operationalisation.

2.3.2 African Empirical Evidence

African empirical studies reveal a persistent gap between HR policy formulation and implementation. Munyoki and Were (2019), studying telecommunications firms in East Africa, reported that although job rotation was formally recognised in HR manuals, implementation guidelines were weak or absent. As a result, rotation was applied selectively, often favouring managerial staff while excluding technical employees.

Amah and Ahiauzu (2019) similarly observed that public-sector organisations in West Africa frequently adopt HR policies to demonstrate compliance with best practices yet lack enforcement mechanisms. Their findings suggest that HR policies without clear operational frameworks often remain symbolic, a pattern relevant to state-owned enterprises such as Zamtel.

2.3.3 Southern African Empirical Evidence

In Southern Africa, empirical evidence shows that job rotation policy effectiveness is strongly influenced by employment structures and labour relations. Chinyamurindi (2017), in a South African public institution study, found that job rotation policies were more effective where they were explicitly linked to promotion criteria and performance appraisal systems. Where such linkages were absent, employees perceived rotation as disruptive rather than developmental.

Masoga and Kaya (2020) further observed that rigid job grading systems in Southern African public organisations limit the flexibility required to operationalise job rotation, reinforcing the need for policies that explicitly accommodate mobility across grades and functions.

2.3.4 Zambian Empirical Evidence

Empirical evidence from Zambia indicates that job rotation is increasingly recognised within human resource policy frameworks, particularly in public sector and state-owned enterprises, as a mechanism for employee development, succession planning, and retention. However, studies consistently show that while job rotation is acknowledged at the policy level, the extent to which it is clearly articulated and operationally guided remains limited.

Mwanza and Phiri (2020), in their study of human resource policy implementation in Zambian state-owned enterprises, found that job rotation was frequently referenced in HR policy documents as a developmental practice but lacked detailed procedural guidelines. Their analysis revealed that policies often failed to specify critical elements such as eligibility criteria, duration of rotation, learning objectives, and links to performance appraisal or promotion. As a result, job rotation provisions were interpreted differently across departments, leading to inconsistencies in application and perceived inequities among employees.

Similarly, Mulenga and Chileshe (2021), examining human resource development practices in Zambian public institutions, reported that HR policies tended to emphasise compliance with best-practice rhetoric rather than actionable frameworks. Their findings showed that job rotation provisions were often embedded within broader training or retention policies without standalone operational clauses. This ambiguity reduced accountability for implementation and weakened the strategic role of job rotation as a structured employee development tool.

Further evidence from the Zambian public service context indicates that HR policy frameworks are often constrained by rigid organisational hierarchies and job classification systems. Chanda and Kabaso (2019) found that although employee mobility was encouraged in policy documents, actual movement across roles was limited by narrowly defined job descriptions and grading structures. This structural rigidity undermined the intent of job rotation provisions and reinforced departmental silos, particularly in technically specialised roles.

Sector-focused studies also suggest that Zambian organisations face challenges in aligning HR policy provisions with evolving skills demands. Phiri and Banda (2019), in their analysis of workforce deployment in Zambia's utilities sector, observed that HR policies recognised the need for skills diversification but did not adequately address the operational risks associated with rotating specialised staff. As a result, job rotation clauses were cautiously worded and rarely supported by detailed implementation strategies.

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Collectively, these Zambian empirical studies demonstrate that while job rotation is formally embedded within human resource policy frameworks, the provisions are often broad, non-specific, and weakly enforced. The absence of detailed operational guidance limits the effectiveness of job rotation as a strategic human capital development tool. This policy-practice disconnect underscores the need for a structured and context-sensitive framework to enhance the operationalisation of job rotation at Zamtel, as pursued in the current study.

2.4 Organisational and Resource-Related Constraints Affecting Operationalisation of Job Rotation

2.4.1 Global Empirical Evidence

Global empirical literature consistently demonstrates that the effectiveness of job rotation policies is constrained less by policy design and more by organisational and resource-related bottlenecks that impede implementation. Drawing on the Theory of Constraints, scholars argue that human resource interventions fail when dominant constraints such as limited training capacity, workload pressures, and managerial resistance are not explicitly identified and managed (Mabin & Balderstone, 2020).

Detert, Schroeder, and Mauriel (2020), in a multi-sector study of strategic execution, found that organisations frequently adopt progressive HR policies but fail to operationalise them due to competing performance pressures and insufficient managerial commitment. In the context of job rotation, the study revealed that line managers often prioritise short-term productivity over long-term capability development, thereby limiting employee mobility across roles. This creates a structural constraint where departments resist releasing staff for rotation due to fear of performance loss.

Similarly, Dechawatanapaisal (2018) demonstrated that unstructured job rotation can introduce role ambiguity and work stress, particularly in highly specialised environments. From a TOC perspective, such negative outcomes reflect failure to subordinate supporting systems such as performance appraisal and workload allocation to the rotation policy. Global evidence therefore suggests that without aligning organisational systems to support rotation, job rotation initiatives become episodic and unsustainable.

2.4.2 African Empirical Evidence

African empirical studies highlight a distinctive set of organisational and resource constraints affecting job rotation, particularly within public and quasi-public institutions. Research across African organisations shows that while job rotation is recognised as a valuable development tool, its implementation is constrained by limited financial resources, weak training infrastructure, and high workload demands (Amah & Ahiauzu, 2019).

Nyathi and Kekwaletswe (2022), studying technology-driven organisations in Africa, identified resource scarcity as a primary constraint limiting job rotation. The study found that organisations lacked sufficient training budgets to support rotation-related learning and mentoring, resulting in superficial role changes without meaningful skills development. This aligns with TOC logic, where financial and capacity constraints restrict throughput of learning across the organisation.

Additionally, African studies point to behavioural constraints, including employee resistance and managerial gatekeeping. Munyoki and Were (2019) observed that managers in African telecommunications firms were reluctant to rotate skilled employees due to concerns about service continuity and skills replacement. This managerial resistance effectively becomes a policy constraint, limiting rotation opportunities despite formal HR provisions.

Collectively, African empirical evidence suggests that job rotation operationalisation is constrained by a combination of resource limitations, managerial discretion, and organisational culture, which must be systematically addressed to realise policy objectives.

2.4.3 Southern African Empirical Evidence

Southern African literature provides deeper insights into how institutional arrangements and labour relations shape job rotation constraints. Studies conducted in South Africa and neighbouring countries show that rigid job grading systems, strong union presence, and formalised employment contracts often limit workforce mobility (Chinyamurindi, 2017; Masoga & Kaya, 2020).

Chinyamurindi (2017) found that employees in Southern African public institutions expressed resistance to job rotation due to fears of unfair performance evaluation, loss of professional identity, and stagnation in promotion pathways. These concerns reflect behavioural constraints that inhibit acceptance of rotation initiatives. From a TOC perspective, such resistance represents a “policy constraint” embedded in organisational culture and reward systems.

Masoga and Kaya (2020) further identified structural constraints arising from narrow job descriptions and rigid grading structures that limit cross-functional movement. Departments with flexible job designs were more capable of implementing job rotation, while those with rigid structures resisted mobility. This resulted in fragmented implementation across organisations, reinforcing silos and undermining integrated capability development.

Southern African empirical evidence therefore underscores the importance of aligning job rotation with labour frameworks, performance management systems, and employee communication strategies to mitigate resistance and structural rigidity.

2.4.4 Zambian Empirical Evidence

In Zambia, organisational and resource-related constraints affecting job rotation are particularly pronounced within state-owned enterprises. Empirical studies indicate that limited training budgets, specialised job roles, and weak succession planning frameworks significantly constrain job rotation implementation (Mwanza & Phiri, 2020; Mulenga & Chileshe, 2021).

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Mwanza and Phiri (2020), examining HR policy implementation in Zambian SOEs, found that job rotation initiatives were frequently deprioritised due to budgetary pressures and competing operational demands. Managers reported reluctance to release experienced employees for rotation due to skills shortages and concerns about service disruption. These findings reflect classic TOC constraints where resource scarcity and skills concentration limit organisational flexibility.

Mulenga and Chileshe (2021) further reported that employees in Zambian public institutions often perceived job rotation as risky to their career progression, particularly where performance appraisal systems did not account for learning curves associated with rotation. This perception contributed to resistance and reduced participation, reinforcing behavioural constraints.

In the telecommunications and utilities sectors, Phiri and Banda (2019) noted that technical roles were least likely to be included in job rotation due to high training costs and critical service requirements. These sector-specific constraints highlight the need for structured frameworks that balance employee development with operational continuity, an issue directly relevant to Zamtel.

2.5 Research gaps

The reviewed literature demonstrates that job rotation is widely recognised as a strategic human resource practice that enhances employee learning, motivation, flexibility, and organisational performance. However, a critical synthesis of global, African, Southern African, Zambian, and telecommunications-industry studies reveals several persistent gaps that justify the current study.

First, there is a contextual gap related to geographic and institutional focus. While extensive empirical evidence exists from Europe, North America, and parts of Asia on the benefits and outcomes of job rotation (Kampkötter et al., 2018; Khan et al., 2021), there is limited empirical research focusing on sub-Saharan African telecommunications firms, particularly state-owned enterprises. African and Southern African studies largely examine job rotation within generic public sector or mixed organisational contexts, offering limited industry-specific insights (Nyathi & Kekwaletswe, 2022; Masoga & Kaya, 2020). Consequently, the applicability of these findings to a Zambian telecommunications organisation such as Zamtel remains under-explored.

Second, an implementation gap is evident in the literature. Most empirical studies focus on the outcomes and benefits of job rotation such as performance, satisfaction, and retention rather than on how job rotation policies are operationalised across departments (Crook et al., 2019; Dechawatanapaisal, 2018). There is limited empirical work examining the translation of job rotation from policy provisions into day-to-day organisational practice, particularly across heterogeneous departments with differing skill requirements. This gap is significant in technically specialised industries like telecommunications, where operational constraints strongly shape implementation.

Third, the literature reveals a theoretical gap in explaining implementation failure. Although Human Capital Theory is widely used to justify job rotation as a development mechanism, fewer studies apply constraint-based theories, such as the Theory of Constraints, to explain why job rotation initiatives fail or are inconsistently implemented (Mabin & Balderstone, 2020). Existing studies often acknowledge barriers such as resource limitations, resistance to change, and skills specialisation but do not systematically analyse these barriers as interacting constraints within an organisational system. This limits theoretical understanding of implementation challenges.

Fourth, there is a departmental and occupational gap in empirical analysis. The reviewed studies consistently indicate that job rotation practices are unevenly applied across organisations, with administrative and managerial staff benefiting more than technical employees (Chen et al., 2020; Munyoki & Were, 2019). However, few studies explicitly examine inter-departmental variation in job rotation implementation and the implications of such variation for organisational learning and equity. This gap is particularly relevant in telecommunications firms where technical departments are critical to service delivery.

Fifth, a policy-practice gap is evident in Zambian and Southern African literature. While HR policies often recognise job rotation as a development and retention strategy, empirical studies indicate that these policies lack detailed operational guidance, resulting in inconsistent application and employee uncertainty (Mwanza & Phiri, 2020; Mulenga & Chileshe, 2021). There is limited research proposing practical, organisation-specific frameworks to bridge this policy-practice divide.

There is a practical framework gap in the literature. Although studies acknowledge the importance of structured job rotation, there is a paucity of research that develops context-specific operational frameworks tailored to industry realities, organisational constraints, and resource limitations. This limits the usefulness of existing literature for practitioners seeking to improve job rotation implementation in real organisational settings.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research philosophy

The study employed interpretive research philosophy. (Bryman & Bell, 2015) explained that interpretive research philosophy emphasizes the subjective interpretation of social phenomena. This approach was appropriate given the study's focus was on understanding the unique cultural, organizational, and social factors that influence the implementation of the job rotation policy within the specific context of Zamtel, a telecommunications company in Lusaka, Zambia (Saunders et al., 2019). The interpretivist philosophy enabled the researcher to capture the subjective experiences, attitudes, and behaviors of Zamtel employees, which are

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crucial in developing a meaningful and contextually relevant framework (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Furthermore, the exploratory and inductive nature of the study, along with the likely use of qualitative A research design is a course of action that guides a researcher in collecting, analyzing and interpreting data and observations to find answers to research questions (Bless and Higson, 1995: 63). data collection methods such as interviews aligned well with the interpretivist approach (Bryman & Bell, 2015; Saunders et al., 2019).

3.2 Research Design

Bless and Higson, 1995: 63) describes a research design as a course of action that directs a researcher in collecting, analyzing and interpreting data and observations to find answers to research questions. The research employed a phenomenological research design, which is particularly effective in exploring phenomena from participants' perspectives. This design enabled the researcher to capture in-depth narratives that unveil the essence of participants' experiences with job rotation strategies. Phenomenological research is beneficial for understanding the lived experiences of participants, including their thoughts, feelings, and attitudes, making it a fitting choice for this study (Sandelowski, 2000). The design emphasized gathering participants' subjective accounts, which illuminated the underlying factors influencing their experiences and perceptions of job rotation at Zamtel. By focusing on these lived experiences, the research aimed to provide rich insights into how job rotation was understood and experienced by the individuals involved.

Table 1: Research design matrix

Research Question	Research Objective	Sampling Technique	Data Collection	Data Analysis
What job rotation provisions are embedded within Zamtel's Human Resource policy framework?	To examine the job rotation provisions embedded within Zamtel's Human Resource policy framework.	Purposive sampling	- Semi-structured interviews with HR representatives - Document analysis of the HR policy	- Content analysis to identify key themes related to the policy coverage and its implications for job rotation practices
What is the extent and nature of job rotation practices implemented across departments at Zamtel?	To assess the extent and nature of job rotation practices implemented across departments at Zamtel.	Purposive sampling	- Semi-structured interviews with department heads - Review of internal documents regarding planned activities	- Content analysis to extract insights on the planned activities, their scope, and alignment with the overall HR strategy
What organisational and resource-related constraints affect the effective operationalisation of the job rotation policy at Zamtel?	To analyse organisational and resource-related constraints that affect the effective operationalisation of the job rotation policy at Zamtel	Purposive sampling	- Semi-structured interviews with department heads - Interviews with HR representatives	- Content analysis to identify bottlenecks and constraints, focusing on organizational, procedural, and resource-related factors affecting implementation

3.3 Research Approach

The study utilized a descriptive qualitative approach, which is characterized by its emphasis on understanding complex phenomena through detailed and context-rich data collection. This approach was chosen to explore participants lived experiences and perspectives regarding job rotation, recognizing that meaning is constructed through individual and collective experiences (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). A descriptive qualitative method is less prescriptive than other qualitative approaches, allowing for an open-ended exploration of ideas and themes as they emerged from participant interviews. This flexibility facilitated an in-depth understanding of the complexities surrounding the job rotation policy and its operationalization within Zamtel.

3.4 Study Area or Site

The study area for the research on enhancing the operationalization of the job rotation policy at Zamtel Head office was Lusaka, Zambia. This selection was justified by several factors: Zamtel's prominence in the Zambian telecommunications sector, Lusaka's status as the economic and administrative center, and the dynamics of the telecommunications industry in the country, and the accessibility and feasibility of data collection in the capital city. As the headquarters of Zamtel was located in Lusaka, the city represented the core of the company's operations and decision-making processes. Focusing the study on Zamtel in Lusaka provided an opportunity to engage directly with the key stakeholders and policy implementers responsible for the job rotation strategy who are housed under one roof, ultimately enabling the development of a comprehensive framework for enhancing the operationalization of the Job rotation policy within the organization.

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3.5 Target Population

The target population for this study consisted of employees from the Zamtel Human Resources department and heads of departments based at the Zamtel Headquarters in Lusaka. The population was selected because the selected individuals are directly involved in decision making, making their insights crucial for understanding its operational challenges (Robinson, 2014). By including a diverse range of roles, the study aimed to capture a spectrum of opinions and experiences, thereby enriching the data collected. This selection aligns with the qualitative emphasis on gathering diverse perspectives to inform the research inquiry more comprehensively.

3.6 Sampling Criteria

Sampling criteria are important to the validity and integrity of a research study. It ensures that the selected participants are represented in a larger population. The sampling criteria that was used in this study employed was criterion purposive sampling. Criterion sampling is a more focused type of purposive sampling where participants are chosen based on strictly defined criteria that are essential to the research question. It offers several benefits for qualitative research, such as facilitating the collection of in-depth data from individuals with relevant experiences, ensuring efficiency by focusing on specific samples, and enabling flexibility to refine criteria as the study progresses (Silverman, 2015). In purposive sampling the focus is only on the group who provide meaningful data. The selected participants under human resources and heads of departments provided relevant expertise and experience that lead to richer insights. Their insights were crucial in the development of a framework as they are directly involved in policy decisions and implementation, including those on job rotation decisions and its impact on employees.

3.7 Sample Size

A total of Fifteen (15) participants were enrolled in the study as key informants. The composition comprised of two (2) employees from Human Resource Department. The Employees from Human Resource Department included the one Director and one Manager. They were key in the study as they facilitate policy development for the management of employees, while the other composition consisted of Heads of Departments representing the thirteen Departments in the organization. The Heads of Departments were key as they are policy Implementors. Creswell (2010) argues that a sample size of 15 to 30 is deemed appropriate for a phenomenological inquiry. For This study, saturation point was used as a basis to arrive at the sample size of 15 in that when the research reached 11 the responses became the same as the one earlier collected. Just to be sure that the responses were the same, 4 more were interviewed and still gave the similar responses

This number strikes a balance between obtaining sufficient data to draw meaningful conclusions and managing the depth of analysis that qualitative research requires. It allows for the collection of rich, detailed accounts while remaining manageable for the researcher to analyze thoroughly. With the size of 15 participants, it was possible to identify recurrent themes and varied experiences without overwhelming the respondents.

Table 2: Represents the distribution of Participants Sample size categorization

No	Position	Department
1	Director Human Resource	Human Resource
2	Manager Human Resource	Human Resource
3	Director Zamtel Money	Zamtel Money
4	Director Financial	Finance
5	Director Commercial 1	Commercial
6	Director Commercial 2	Commercial
7	Director Technical	Technical
8	Director Information	Information Technology
9	Director Auditor	Audit
10	Director Commercial 3	Commercial
11	Director Risk	Risk
12	Director Planning	Strategy
13	Director Legal	Legal & Corporate Services Officer
14	Director Support Services	Corporate Support Services
15	Director Supply Chain	Supply Chain

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3.8 Procedure for Data Collection Instruments

Data collection for the study was conducted through semi-structured interviews, offering a flexible yet guided methodology to explore participants' experiences and opinions regarding job rotation (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015). This approach was selected to facilitate the emergence of detailed and nuanced responses, allowing participants to elaborate on their thoughts and feelings while addressing specific themes related to the job rotation strategy.

The semi-structured format encouraged open dialogue, providing participants with the opportunity to express their views in their own words, which ultimately enriched the data that was collected. Interviews were conducted in a manner that ensured participants felt comfortable sharing their insights, promoting an authentic and honest exchange of information. To achieve this, the researcher created a relaxed environment, establishing rapport through preliminary conversations and ensuring confidentiality, which facilitated more candid responses.

In addition to the primary data gathered through interviews, secondary sources were also utilized to supplement the research findings. This included reviewing existing organizational documents, and previous studies related to job rotation strategies in the telecommunications sector. This combination of qualitative interviews and secondary data sources ensured a comprehensive understanding of the topic, allowing for triangulation of the findings and enhancing the overall validity and reliability of the research. By integrating different types of data, the study aimed to provide a well-rounded perspective on the operationalization of job rotation strategies at Zamtel.

Below is a summary of steps taken during data collection procedure.

Step 1: Prior to the interviews being conducted, formal requests of invitation were sent to the selected interviewees to ask them to participate, and this was done using the telephone, to which all 15 participants agreed.

Step 2: Implementation: On the scheduled days, the processes were as follows. The interviews started with formal introductions to establish relationships. In this same vein of matters of anonymity were discussed, and the participants' rights were read through to them, such as the right to disengage if they felt uncomfortable with the topic or how the process was being conducted. At this point, they were asked if it was alright with them if the tape recorder could be used to record the proceedings, and the reasons for doing so were given. Permission was granted.

Step 3: Questions: The series of questions started with warm-up general questions to establish rapport before getting into the thrust of the discussion.

Step 4: Closing: To signify the ending of the session, cool-off questions were asked to diffuse any tensions and finish on contentious issues. The sessions ended by thanking the participants for sparing their time to participate in the study.

3.9 In-depth Interview Schedule

An in-depth interview schedule is a structured plan or guide that researchers use to facilitate qualitative interviews, allowing them to gather detailed, rich data from participants about their experiences, opinions, feelings, and behaviors regarding a specific topic (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015). The schedule typically includes open-ended questions and prompts designed to encourage participants to share their insights in their own words while maintaining a focus on the study's objectives.

The purpose of an in-depth interview schedule was to ensure that the conversation was focused, yet flexible enough to allow for exploration of unexpected themes that may arise during the interview process. This approach enables researchers to probe deeper into participants' responses, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter (McIntosh & Morse, 2015).

In the context of the study on the operationalization of the job rotation strategy at Zamtel, the in-depth interview schedule was developed based on the key themes identified in the literature about job rotation, employee engagement, and organizational effectiveness.

The researcher conducted semi-structured interviews with employees, utilizing the interview schedule to guide the conversation while allowing participants to express their experiences freely. The interviews were designed to capture the details of the participants' perceptions about the job rotation policy, including their feelings, experience towards the effectiveness of the implementation, challenges faced, and suggestions for improvements. By employing this method, the research aimed to gain a deeper understanding of how job rotation impacted employee engagement and satisfaction within the organization. The researcher also incorporated secondary data sources to complement the primary data obtained from the interviews. This combination provided a richer context and validated findings through triangulation reinforcing the insights gathered about job rotation practices at Zamtel. During the interview process records for each participant were given a unique code. The codes for Heads of Departments and the employees from Human Resources were denoted with symbols from HD1 to HD15

3.10 Data Analysis

The collected data was analyzed using content analysis, a method that involves identifying, analyzing, and reporting themes within qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This approach was chosen for its flexibility and applicability to descriptive qualitative research, allowing the researcher to dissect complex narratives into salient themes that reflect commonalities and divergences in

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participants' experiences. The analysis process involved familiarization with the data, coding relevant sections, and grouping codes into broader themes that elucidate the participants' insights regarding the job rotation strategy. This systematic approach not only ensured rigor and validity in qualitative analysis but also facilitated for an understanding of the broader implications of job rotation practices at Zamtel, providing a comprehensive framework for potential policy enhancements. Table 8 below illustrates the procedure conducted for Content analysis.

Table 3: Content Analysis Procedure

SN	Procedure Item	Procedure Process
1	Familiarization	The researcher began by immersing themselves in the qualitative data, reading through interview transcripts and notes to gain a comprehensive understanding of the content. This initial step helped in recognizing recurring ideas and sentiments expressed by participants
2	Coding	Relevant sections of the data were then coded, where specific phrases or sentences were tagged with labels that captured the essence of the content. For example, phrases related to employee engagement were coded as "engagement" or "motivation," allowing for systematic categorization. Once coding was complete, similar codes were grouped into broader themes. For instance, codes like "engagement," "team collaboration," and "job satisfaction" were consolidated under a theme titled "Employee Well-being."
3	Theme Development	Finally, the researcher analyzed these themes to draw insights about participants' experiences. This involved interpreting how the identified themes reflected the overall effectiveness of job rotation strategies and their implications for policy enhancements at Zamtel

3.11 Validity and Reliability

This section introduces reliability and validity which are crucial in a qualitative inquiry in ensuring the stand of quality and trustworthiness are maintained. The concepts form the foundation for evaluating the rigor in the research design and findings. Unlike in quantitative research where reliability and validity are well-defined in numerical terms qualitative research adopts an interpretive approach with the aim of exploring an in depth understanding from perspective participants.

3.11.1 Validity

The validity of this process was ensured by making sure that the level of rigor was high. This included using well-established qualitative research methods, such as semi-structured interviews, to collect rich and detailed data from the participants. The researcher also triangulated the interview data with a review of relevant internal organizational documents to collaborate into the findings for a comprehensive understanding of the job rotation at Zamtel.

Furthermore, the researcher engaged in member checking, where the preliminary findings were shared with the participants from Human resource department and the heads of departments to verify the accuracy of the interpretations and allow for any necessary clarifications or corrections. This process helped to enhance the credibility and trustworthiness of the study's conclusions.

3.11.2 Reliability

To ensure reliability, the study employed criterion purposive sampling to select fifteen (15) participants who held senior positions in the organization and were interviewed. The rationale behind this sampling approach was that the departmental heads and human resource representatives were knowledgeable about the phenomena under investigation, its implementation and the associated challenges. By targeting these key informants, the researcher could obtain reliable and informed perspectives on the operationalization of the job rotation strategy at Zamtel.

Additionally, the researcher developed a detailed interview schedule to guide the data collection process, ensuring consistency in the questions asked and the information gathered across the different participants. This standardized approach contributed to the overall reliability of the study's findings.

The chapter above presented a qualitative methodology that was adopted in the study to explore job rotation at Zamtel. The study employed interpretivist, phenomenological design with a criterion purposive sampling of 15 key informants. The key insights into the required information were collected through semi structured interviews and analyzed through content analysis aiming to understand the employee experiences.

3.12 Trustworthiness of Qualitative Data

In qualitative research, trustworthiness is critical to ensure that the findings are credible, dependable, confirmable, and transferable. To enhance the trustworthiness of the data in this study, several strategies were employed.

First, credibility was ensured through the use of in-depth interviews with key informants who had direct experience with the implementation of the job rotation strategy within Zamtel. Participants included departmental heads and relevant employees who were knowledgeable about human resource practices within their departments. The use of open-ended interview questions allowed participants to provide detailed explanations of their experiences, thereby generating rich and meaningful data. In addition, probing techniques were used during interviews to clarify responses and obtain deeper insights into the operationalisation of job rotation practices.

Secondly, dependability was ensured by maintaining a clear and transparent research process. The researcher documented the procedures followed during data collection and analysis, including the development of interview guides, data coding processes, and thematic analysis procedures. This documentation provides an audit trail that allows other researchers to understand how the findings were derived and enhances the reliability of the research process.

Thirdly, confirmability was strengthened by ensuring that the findings were grounded in the data collected from participants rather than the researcher's personal biases or assumptions. Direct quotations from participants were incorporated into the analysis to demonstrate how interpretations were derived from the responses provided by the interviewees. This approach ensured that the results reflected the participants' perspectives regarding the implementation of the job rotation strategy within the organisation.

Finally, transferability was addressed by providing a detailed description of the research context, including the organisational setting, the nature of the job rotation policy, and the characteristics of the participants involved in the study. By clearly describing the context of the research, other scholars and practitioners can assess the extent to which the findings may be applicable to similar organisational environments within the telecommunications sector or other public institutions.

Through these measures, the study ensured that the qualitative data collected were credible, reliable, and reflective of the participants' experiences, thereby strengthening the overall validity of the research findings.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter consists of various types of findings based on the data that was collected. It starts by tackling the background characteristics, which are followed by findings according to the objectives. Other supplementary findings are also presented, after which a summary of the chapter is done.

4.1 Response rate of the Participants

A total number of 15 participants were interviewed in this qualitative study, the participants were selected using criterion purposive sampling, ensuring that they met specific criteria relevant to the research objectives. The number of participants was adequate to reach thematic saturation level.

All fifteen participants who were invited to take part in the study met the selection criteria and consented to participate, resulting in a 100% response rate. The use of criterion purposive sampling ensured that participants possessed direct knowledge of human resource policy implementation and departmental practices. The sample size was adequate for a qualitative inquiry, as thematic saturation was reached, with no substantially new insights emerging in the later interviews. This enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the findings.

4.2 Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Information was obtained from a varied mixed tenure of a total of 15 key informants who participated in the study. The key information provided a multigenerational balance on Zamtel's operation. The key information on the number of years in the organization such HD2 (30 years), HD15 (30 years), and HD14 (14 years) provided insights and depth of experience guided by institutional memory which meant that they witnessed various policy shifts and organizational transition. Their insights were valuable for understanding long-term trends. While the mid-range provided a balance in understanding Zamtel's current internal operations. While the newer staff in the category of HD1 (3 years), HD6 (4 years), HD8 (4 years), and HD13 (for less than 1 year) Their contribution did not go unnoticed as they provided insights into the current experiences of employee onboarding experiences and integration. The figure below illustrates the length of service of the respondents

Figure 1: Respondents' length of service
Source: The Author.2025

The demographic composition of participants reflected a diverse mix of organisational tenure, enabling the study to capture both historical and contemporary perspectives on job rotation. Participants with long service, such as HD2 and HD15 (30 years) and HD14 (14 years), provided insights grounded in institutional memory, having witnessed multiple organisational transitions and policy shifts. Their accounts were critical in understanding the evolution of human resource practices over time. Participants with mid-range tenure offered balanced perspectives on both policy intent and operational realities, while newer employees, including HD1, HD6, HD8, and HD13, contributed valuable insights into onboarding experiences and early exposure to job rotation practices. This generational diversity enriched the analysis by revealing how job rotation is perceived and experienced differently across tenure groups.

4.3 Job Rotation Provisions Embedded in Human Resource Policy Frameworks

This section of the chapter addressed the research question "What job rotation provisions are embedded within Zamtel's Human Resource policy framework?" This section was important as it gave a call to understand the starting point of assessing the existing policy, that is if the job rotation strategy had clearly defined objectives, specific roles, departments to take part in the job rotation and a structured program in place. It also provided a framework for verifying what was missing or ineffective. The following main themes emerged which included: Which Departments are eligible for Job Rotation under the Job Rotation strategy? Which job types does the policy include in its job rotation strategy and the subthemes included: flexibility based on skill sets and Structured Programs and Communication before a section summary was drawn.

4.3.1 Theme 1: Departments that are eligible for Job Rotation under the Job Rotation Strategy

The theme above addressed the question: "From the time the Human Resource retention policy was rolled out, how many employees have experienced job rotation from your department?" An examination of departmental participation in job rotation provided insight into the distribution of employee development opportunities across the organisation. The findings revealed uneven implementation of the job rotation strategy across departments, reflecting differences in departmental functions, staffing levels, and skills requirements, which significantly influenced the application of the policy.

Notably, HD5 reported that no employees from their department had participated in job rotation, stating, "Our department is specialised and requires expertise. Therefore, rotations may not be feasible." This response suggests that highly specialised departments lacked the flexibility required for job rotation, thereby limiting opportunities for broader skills exposure, particularly for new entrants.

Similarly, HD3 indicated that no employees had experienced job rotation from their department, explaining, "Our department is different; we are very few with specified roles." This highlights how small departmental size and role specificity constrained participation in the job rotation programme.

In contrast, HD1 and HD2 reported that "a combined total of 20 employees from their departments had experienced job rotation since the rollout of the Human Resource retention policy in 2021, indicating that departments with broader role structures and larger staffing complements were more able to participate in the job rotation initiative".

The findings reveal that job rotation is unevenly applied across departments, largely influenced by departmental function, size, and skill specialisation. Highly specialised and small departments reported that there was no participation in job rotation, citing the need for continuity and expertise. In contrast, departments with broader role structures and larger staffing complements reported higher levels of participation. This variation suggested that while the policy exists at organisational level, its application was contingent on

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departmental discretion, leading to unequal access to developmental opportunities. The findings pointed to a policy–practice gap, where the absence of standardised eligibility criteria allows operational realities to override policy intent.

Figure 3: Represents the number of employees
Source: The Author.2025

4.3.2 Theme 2: Job types eligible for job rotation

This theme addressed the question: “What measures have you put in place to ensure that new entrants in the organisation are rotated in your department?” The question was critical in identifying job types eligible for inclusion in the job rotation programme, recognising that not all roles require the same skill sets or allow for similar levels of mobility. The findings indicated that job rotation practices were shaped by the nature of job roles, operational demands, and departmental strategies, resulting in varied approaches to rotating new entrants across the organisation.

The data revealed that departments adopted different measures to facilitate job rotation for new employees. For example, HD8 explained that structured systems were in place to support rotation, stating, “I ensure a structured onboarding programme that includes cross-functional attachment, mentorship, and regular performance evaluations to track progress and skill development.” This approach reflected the need for deliberate effort to integrate job rotation into onboarding processes as a means of developing employee competencies and monitoring learning outcomes.

Similarly, HD3 reported an alternative approach, noting that “New joiners in the department are assigned engagements with different departments every quarter. Employees from our department don’t go to the other departments, but they learn from colleagues from other departments who mentor them.” This indicated that while physical rotation may not occur, knowledge transfer is facilitated through inter-departmental interactions and mentoring arrangements.

In contrast, some departments reported limited scope for job rotation due to the specialised nature of their roles. HD5 maintained that “Our department is specialised and requires expertise. Therefore, rotations may not be feasible,” reinforcing the view that certain job types demand high levels of technical competence and continuity, thereby restricting rotational opportunities.

Additionally, HD4 indicated that alternative human resource practices were used in place of job rotation, stating, “We have been using much of job enrichment and expansion instead of rotation. Rotation is usually done for duty officers who take up responsibilities over the weekends and long holidays.” This response suggested that job rotation was applied selectively to specific categories of employees, particularly duty officers, rather than across all job types.

Further analysis revealed that employees in the Commercial and Technical departments, particularly those at lower to middle levels, were more likely to be eligible for job rotation. This eligibility was attributed to the versatility of skills within these roles, which allowed employees to transition more easily across functions. As noted by HD4, “New entrants especially are put on a programme of job rotation to ensure they understand the business before they can even settle in one role.” This underscored the strategic use of job rotation to provide new employees with a holistic understanding of organisational operations. Moreover, the operational

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demands of these roles necessitated broader functional exposure, making job rotation a valuable tool for enhancing organisational efficiency.

As HD5 explained, "Each employee is given tasks for a given duration and appraised based on the achieved KPIs against the set objectives," highlighting the use of structured performance management to support rotational assignments.

Analysis of job types eligible for job rotation shows that eligibility is largely role-dependent rather than policy-driven. Departments adopted varied approaches to rotating new entrants, ranging from structured onboarding with cross-functional attachments to indirect exposure through mentoring arrangements. In specialised departments, job rotation was largely replaced with job enrichment or limited to specific categories such as duty officers. This selective approach indicates that job rotation is not universally conceptualised as a developmental tool, but rather as an optional practice applied where operationally convenient. The findings further suggested that commercial and technical roles at lower to middle levels were more likely to be considered suitable for rotation due to skill versatility and operational interdependence.

4.3.3 Subtheme 1: flexibility based on skill sets.

There was an acknowledgment that some departments, particularly specialized ones, would face challenges with Job rotations. To be specific, H5 noted, "Our department is specialised and requires expertise. Therefore, rotations may not be feasible." However, other departments were flexible, as revealed by H10, the finding showed that "Based on performance reviews, job rotation takes effect." This adaptability allowed for rotations tailored to the employees' abilities and departmental requirements. This revealed that the implementation of the job rotation strategy since its rollout was not uniform across the departments. With variation it broadened a challenging gap in achieving equitable employee development opportunities across the organization.

This comprehensive look at the job rotation strategies showed that Zamtel acknowledged the need for tailored approaches that considered both employee growth and departmental requirements. Although the policy was designed to enhance the benefits of job rotation, its inconsistent application across departments illustrated the challenge of balancing operational needs with the developmental objectives.

Flexibility based on employee skill sets emerged as a critical determinant of job rotation implementation. Departments that linked rotation decisions to performance reviews and demonstrated adaptability in role assignment were more likely to implement job rotation. Conversely, departments with rigid skill requirements exhibited resistance to rotation. This highlights a tension between developmental objectives and operational efficiency, where the need to maintain specialised expertise constrains employee mobility. The lack of a formal framework to guide skill-based rotation decisions contributed to inconsistent application and limited equitable access to rotation opportunities.

4.3.4 Theme 3: Structured Programs and Communication

Some departments had implemented formal job rotation programs to ensure that new employees gain a broad understanding of the organizations Job rotation. For example, H4 mentioned, "Planned rotation program-Formal structure for job rotation is in place," which indicated a systematic approach to integrating new entrants into various roles.

While effective communication ensures that the importance of rotations is emphasized. The findings revealed that H7 noted that clear communication is essential for "employees need to understand the importance of departmental job rotations." Additionally, H8 stated, "Through Team building for each one to appreciate what others are doing," which fosters collaboration and a better understanding of different roles within the organization. HR1 added that "At induction, employees are made aware of the rotation plan.

Communication is key when conducting job rotation. It enhances teamwork and Cross-functional collaboration, which is vital in all roles. HD7 pointed out, "Through collaborative team building, each one can appreciate what others are doing," emphasizing the collaborative spirit fostered through communication.

The analysis shows that structured programmes and effective communication play a central role in supporting job rotation. Departments with formal rotation programmes, clear onboarding structures, and proactive communication were better able to integrate new employees and promote cross-functional understanding. Communication was found to enhance employee acceptance of rotation by clarifying its purpose and benefits, while team-based initiatives fostered collaboration and appreciation of inter-departmental roles. However, the absence of organisation-wide standards resulted in fragmented implementation, reinforcing the need for standardisation.

4.4 Extent and Nature of Job Rotation Practices Implemented Across Departments

This section addressed the research question "What is the extent and nature of job rotation practices implemented across departments at Zamtel?" This section was important as it gave a call to examine the job rotation activities that were in place and check if the current activities were aligned with the strategic intent. The main themes that emerged was Appraisal approaches following job rotation and duration of stay in a rotated role and the subthemes included: Comprehensive Feedback Mechanisms and Standardized Performance Management Systems.

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4.4.1 Theme 4: Appraisal approaches following job rotation.

To answer the question "How are employees appraised after a job rotation in your department"? The other question: Have you differentiated the manner and content areas of appraisal of rotated employees from non-rotated employees?

The findings on the differentiation in appraisal methods for rotated employees compared to non-rotated employees revealed nuanced approaches among various departments, with some clear distinctions noted.

The appraisal process often included personalized discussions to promote development. HD6 stated, "An appraisal form is filled out thereafter, one on one discussions are held." These discussions enabled a deeper understanding of the employee's experience during the rotation, focusing on skills gained, challenges faced, and future development opportunities. This approach fostered a supportive environment where employees could discuss their career path and aspirations.

Responses from other respondents confirmed that rotated employees were appraised with specific tasks and objectives tailored to their assigned roles. As revealed by HD5, "Each employee has specific tasks and objectives set apart from the general terms that applies to all," indicating that the appraisals for rotated employees are not generic but are instead aligned with their current responsibilities. In contrast, non-rotated employees receive evaluations based primarily on their established roles and expertise, which was reflected in a statement given by HD10 stating, "non-rotated employees are assessed based on their expertise and performance within their specific functions." This indicated a more fixed approach to assessment for employees who remained in their original roles.

A key difference highlighted by HD4 was that rotated employees receive feedback from multiple supervisors, whereas non-rotated employees typically report to a single supervisor: "Rotated employees receive feedback from various supervisors as opposed to one direct supervisor for non-rotated employees." This multifaceted feedback system for rotated staff allowed for a broader perspective on their performance and adaptability.

Other responses indicated that appraisals for rotated employees emphasized adaptability, and the application of new skills learned across different roles. HD6 mentioned, "I evaluate rotated staff on their adaptability and ability to apply learnings across various roles," showcasing how their evaluations are geared towards measuring their versatility within the organization. Conversely, non-rotated employees' evaluations are often tied to their long-term role expertise and consistency in performance, as revealed by HD8, who stated that, "non-rotated employees focus on expertise and consistency in their assigned roles." This implies that a standard expectation of proven competence over time.

There was an indication that rotated employees had a deeper understanding of the organization's goals due to their varied experiences. HD9 observed that "the rotated employees tend to be more involved in the daily tasks as they seem to appreciate more the goals we are aiming at." This suggested that exposure to different roles enhances their engagement and alignment with organizational objectives.

The insights directly responded to the research question. The finding demonstrated a clear difference in appraisal approaches with the rotated employees assessed based on their contribution, while non-rotated employees are appraised based on their expertise.

The findings indicate that appraisal practices for rotated employees differ from those for non-rotated employees, reflecting recognition of the unique learning demands associated with rotation. Rotated employees were appraised using role-specific objectives, adaptability, and feedback from multiple supervisors, whereas non-rotated employees were assessed based on expertise within fixed roles. This differentiated approach suggests an appreciation of learning curves and skill acquisition. However, the absence of uniform appraisal guidelines created inconsistencies in how rotated employees were evaluated across departments.

4.4.2 Theme 5: Duration of stay in a rotated role.

To answer the question "Please explain to me how long you have planned for an employee to remain in a new location when they are rotated" The findings revealed that some departments the practice was observational in nature for instance taking into consideration the duration of the rotation H9 stated that the rotation in his department lasted for "3 weeks". Conversely, other departments reported that they either did practice HD3 "we don't practice job rotation" and other departments did not plan for the exercise HD5 revealed that "We haven't planned due to the nature of the department" Although at the same time the report revealed a balance and a need for operational continuity and employee developmental balance. "HD12 stated that probation lasts for at least 6 months in our department, if they perform well, they can be recommended"

Analysis revealed a lack of standardisation in the duration of job rotation, with reported rotation periods ranging from a few weeks to several months, while some departments did not practice rotation at all. Decisions regarding duration were largely observational and department-specific, reflecting operational convenience rather than policy guidance. This inconsistency undermines the developmental potential of job rotation and highlights the need for clear organisational guidelines to balance operational continuity with learning objectives.

Figure 4: Provides a summary of the duration of stay in the departments.
Source: The Author.2025

Following the analysis on the appraisal approaches following job rotation and duration of stay in a rotated role other theme that emerged, and they were arranged as subthemes. These were categorized into two key subthemes as follows: Comprehensive Feedback Mechanisms, Standardized Performance Management Systems, Standardized Performance Management Systems.

4.4.3 Subtheme 1: Comprehensive Feedback Mechanisms

Feedback plays a crucial role in the appraisal process. Employees are encouraged to provide insights into their experiences during rotations. HD7 highlighted that "they fill in some forms as part of their feedback on their experience," indicating an emphasis on capturing employee perspectives. Moreover, the inclusion of feedback from supervisors and colleagues contributes to a holistic assessment of an employee's learning progress and overall contribution, as reflected in HD9: "Feedback from supervisors and colleagues helps assess their learning progress and overall contribution. "Importantly, it was noted by HD12 that there remains uncertainty in standard practices for appraising different employee categories. One respondent mentioned, "Since I have not done this, my recommendation to HR is that they come up with a guideline to aid the process," indicating a recognized need for clearer guidelines to differentiate the appraisal processes effectively.

Feedback mechanisms were recognised as important components of the job rotation process, enabling employees to reflect on their experiences and contribute insights for improvement. While some departments utilised structured feedback tools and standard performance management systems, others lacked clarity on appraisal processes for rotated employees. The reliance on standard PMS frameworks without rotation-specific adaptations limited the effectiveness of performance evaluation in capturing learning outcomes, reinforcing calls for clearer guidelines.

4.4.4 Subtheme 2: Standardized Performance Management Systems

The use of standardized performance management appraisal systems (PMS) was evident in multiple departments. HD2 noted, "Through performance management appraisal," indicating the implementation of a formal framework for evaluating employee contributions. Additionally, HD8 mentioned, "Using the standard PMS reviews done quarterly," highlighting that evaluations are consistent and periodically reviewed to track progress over time.

Employees are assessed not only based on their core tasks but also on their performance in the new roles they take up during job rotations. HD5 commented, "They are appraised on the tasks they were assigned, not their core tasks." This points to a targeted evaluation strategy that measures how well employees adjust and contribute to their temporary roles, ensuring they were recognized.

4.5 Organisational and Resource-Related Constraints Affecting Operationalisation of Job Rotation

This section addressed the research question "What organisational and resource-related constraints affect the effective operationalisation of the job rotation policy at Zamtel? This section was important because the non-operationalized job rotation strategy in the retention policy suggested a disconnect with the daily practice as such there was a need to understand the gaps.

Job rotation is a strategic human resource tool that not only enhances employee skills engagement and motivation but also greatly contributes to employee retention. It was revealed that Zamtel has a job rotation strategy that has potential to motivate its employees.

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However, several operational challenges limited its effectiveness. By identifying the key challenges that hindered the implementation of the full job rotation strategy the following themes emerged: budget constraints and implications, staff quality to implement job rotation, staff attitudes towards job rotation and staff quantities available for rotation. To address each identified challenges the proposed solutions were shared to strengthen employee retention.

4.5.1 Theme 6: Budget Constraints and Implications

To Answer the question "What challenges do you think are hindering the implementation of the Job Rotation Strategy?" "The findings revealed that identified budgetary constraints were a significant barrier to effective job rotation. HD2 remarked, "Financial constraints limit our ability to implement comprehensive rotation programs. We often have to prioritize core activities."

HD1 emphasized the point, "Without sufficient funding, it's challenging to provide the necessary training and resources for effective job rotations." This suggests that without adequate funding, the organization struggles to fully realize its job rotation initiatives.

Budget constraints were discovered to be one standing in the path to a successful implementation of a job rotation strategy. Budget allocations in an organization will often Favour operational activities over employee development like job rotation. As highlighted by one of the HD2 'financial limitations restrict the organization's ability to roll out comprehensive rotation programs, often forcing prioritization of core activities over developmental initiatives.' To address this issue, it is crucial for Zamtel to seek additional funding through strategic budget allocation. By conducting budget reallocation and presenting different compelling fund sourcing cases to different stakeholders on the long-term benefits of job rotation. When funds are allocated for this exercise, employees can have the opportunity to develop career opportunities. This can signal the value an organization has for employees, in turn making the organization attractive.

Budgetary limitations emerged as a dominant constraint, restricting training, mentoring, and support structures necessary for effective job rotation. Developmental initiatives were often not prioritised in favour of core operational activities, limiting long-term capability building.

4.5.2 Theme 7: Staff Quality to Implement Job Rotation

To Answer the question "Do you need dedicated staff with the right skills to manage Job rotations?" "The need for skilled personnel to manage job rotation initiatives was emphasized. HD2 stated, "We need to provide training to prepare employees for their new roles; otherwise, they might struggle." HD1 added, "Some employees feel unprepared when they switch positions, which can lead to frustration and inefficiency." This indicated that investing in training is crucial for the successful implementation of job rotation. The quality of staff available to implement job rotation initiatives is paramount for the success of a job rotation program. Participants have emphasized the necessity of investing in targeted training programs to enhance employee skills and competencies, ensuring that they are well-prepared for effective role transitions. Without adequate training, employees may feel unprepared and struggle when switching positions, leading to frustration and inefficiency. By focusing on developing a robust training framework tailored to the specific skills required for various roles, Zamtel can ensure that employees are equipped to navigate the challenges of job rotation, thereby maximizing the benefits of this strategic initiative and increasing job satisfaction.

The availability of adequately skilled staff to manage and participate in rotations was identified as a key challenge. Without sufficient training and preparation, employees struggled to transition into new roles, reducing the effectiveness of rotation initiatives.

4.5.3 Theme 8: Staff Attitudes towards Job Rotation

To Answer the question "what is the feeling for employees towards Job Rotation the organization?" "The readiness and mindset of employees towards job changes emerged as a crucial theme. HD2 remarked, "Many employees are hesitant to embrace job changes due to fear of the unknown. It's a common concern." HD1 echoed this sentiment, stating, "There's a perception that moving around might hinder career progression, which creates resistance." This highlights a common fear among employees that can prevent them from engaging with rotation opportunities.

Employee attitudes towards job rotation play a critical role in its successful implementation. Many employees' express hesitation in embracing job changes due to fear of the unknown and concerns about potential career impacts. To foster a more positive outlook, it is essential for Zamtel to cultivate a culture of openness by effectively communicating the benefits of job rotation. Management should reassure employees that participation in rotation programs can lead to skill enhancement and career advancement opportunities. By addressing these concerns and highlighting the value of job rotation for personal and professional growth, Zamtel can encourage greater participation and mitigate resistance among its workforces.

Employee resistance, driven by fear of the unknown and concerns about career progression, further constrained implementation. These attitudes reflect insufficient communication and reassurance regarding the developmental value of job rotation.

4.5.4 Theme 9: Staff Quantities Available for Rotation

To answer the question 'How does the staff availability of staff across the department impact the effectiveness of job rotation. The availability of employees for rotation is crucial for the successful execution of the job rotation policy. Without sufficient or appropriately skilled staff. Job rotation can be limited. Current findings indicate that some departments, such as HD11 and HD5,

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reported zero rotations due to the specialized nature of their work. To enhance operationalization, Zamtel should develop a structured rotation plan that identifies suitable roles for rotation and allocates sufficient employees across departments.

This plan must consider the unique needs of each department while ensuring that rotations are feasible and do not disrupt ongoing operations. Zamtel can maximize the benefits of job rotation, promoting employee development and organizational flexibility. Limited staffing levels in specialised departments reduced the feasibility of rotation, reinforcing the need for strategic workforce planning to support employee mobility without disrupting operations.

Figure 5: Enhancing Job Rotation Strategy for Improved Employee Retention
Source: The Author.2025

4.5.5 Chapter Summary

The chapter presented a complete analysis of the Job Rotation strategy at Zamtel, with detailed findings on the Job Rotation Provisions Embedded in Human Resource Policy Frameworks Extent and Nature of Job Rotation Practices Implemented across Departments and Organisational and Resource-related constraints Affecting Operationalisation of Job Rotation

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study established that Zamtel has formally embedded job rotation within its Human Resource retention policy; however, the policy lacks operational clarity and consistency. The findings revealed that job rotation provisions are broadly stated, with limited guidance on departmental eligibility, job types, rotation duration, and appraisal mechanisms. Consequently, implementation is left largely to departmental discretion.

Further study found that job rotation practices at Zamtel are unevenly implemented across departments. Departments with broader role structures and sufficient staffing levels were more likely to implement job rotation, while specialised and small departments reported little to no participation. In several cases, alternative practices such as job enrichment, mentoring, and cross-functional exposure were used in place of formal job rotation.

In addition, the study identified multiple organisational and resource-related constraints that have hindered the effective operationalisation of the job rotation strategy. These included budgetary limitations, insufficient training capacity, staff shortages, skills specialisation, employee resistance, and lack of standardised implementation frameworks. These constraints interacted with limiting the full realisation of the intended benefits of job rotation.

5.2 Conclusions

5.2.1 Conclusion in Relation to Research Objective One

The study concludes that Zamtel's Human Resource policy formally recognises job rotation as a strategic employee development and retention tool. This objective was achieved through a systematic examination of policy content and participant perceptions, which confirmed the presence of job rotation provisions. However, the policy lacks detailed operational guidelines, including clear eligibility criteria, structured rotation processes, and explicit links to performance management and career progression. As a result,

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the policy provides strategic intent but insufficient direction for consistent implementation, limiting its effectiveness as a human capital development instrument.

5.2.2 Conclusion in Relation to Research Objective Two

The study concludes that job rotation practices at Zamtel are inconsistently applied and vary significantly across departments. This objective was achieved by analysing departmental experiences and practices, which revealed that job rotation is more prevalent in departments with flexible role structures and lower technical specialisation. In contrast, specialised departments either do not practice job rotation or apply it selectively. The absence of standardised rotation duration, appraisal approaches, and uniform participation has resulted in unequal access to developmental opportunities and reduced the strategic impact of job rotation across the organisation.

5.2.3 Conclusion in Relation to Research Objective Three

The study concluded that the effective operationalisation of the job rotation strategy at Zamtel is constrained by interrelated organisational and resource limitations. This objective was achieved by identifying and analysing key constraints, including budgetary pressures, staff shortages, skills specialisation, limited training capacity, employee resistance, and managerial reluctance. These constraints collectively inhibit implementation and reinforce inconsistency across departments. The findings demonstrate that without addressing these systemic constraints, the job rotation strategy cannot achieve its intended developmental and retention outcomes.

5.3 Recommendations

5.3.1 Policy and Strategic Recommendations

Zamtel should revise its Human Resource policy to include a clearly articulated job rotation framework. This framework should define eligibility criteria, scope of rotation, duration, learning objectives, and links to performance management and career progression. A standardised framework will reduce departmental discretion and promote equitable access to job rotation opportunities.

5.3.2 Operational Recommendations

Zamtel should develop and implement department-sensitive job rotation models, recognising differences between technical and non-technical functions. Where physical rotation is not feasible due to skills specialisation, structured alternatives such as shadowing, cross-functional projects, and rotational assignments with defined learning outcomes should be formalised and monitored.

5.3.3 Resource and Capacity-Building Recommendations

The organisation should allocate dedicated budgetary resources to support job rotation, including training, mentoring, and supervision. Investment in employee capacity-building will enhance readiness for rotation and reduce resistance associated with skills gaps and performance uncertainty.

5.3.4 Change Management and Communication Recommendations

Zamtel should strengthen internal communication and change management strategies to improve employee understanding and acceptance of job rotation. Clear communication on the benefits of job rotation, its role in career development, and safeguards against negative career implications will help address employee resistance.

5.3.5 Monitoring and Evaluation Recommendations

The organisation should integrate job rotation into the performance management system, ensuring that rotated employees are assessed using role-specific objectives and multi-source feedback. Regular monitoring and evaluation will enable management to track outcomes, identify challenges, and continuously improve the job rotation strategy.

5.4 Areas for Further Research

Future studies may adopt a mixed-methods approach to quantify the impact of job rotation on employee performance and retention at Zamtel. Comparative studies involving other telecommunications firms or state-owned enterprises in Zambia and the Southern African region would also provide broader insights into best practices for operationalising job rotation strategies.

5.5 Study Limitations

Despite the valuable insights generated from this study, several limitations were identified which informed the recommendations presented in this research. First, the study was conducted within a single organization, Zamtel in Lusaka, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other organisations within the telecommunications sector or the broader public sector in Zambia. Organizational structures, human resource policies, and operational environments vary across institutions, which means the findings may reflect context-specific conditions. This limitation supports the recommendation for future comparative studies involving other organizations in order to identify best practices and improve the operationalisation of job rotation strategies across different institutional contexts.

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Secondly, the study relied primarily on qualitative data collected from departmental heads and selected employees, which provided in-depth insights but may not fully represent the perspectives of all employees within the organisation. Some departments had limited participation due to operational demands, which may have restricted the diversity of views captured regarding the implementation of job rotation. This limitation informed the recommendation that future studies should adopt mixed-method approaches, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative data to capture broader employee perceptions and strengthen the robustness of the findings.

Another limitation relates to the availability of documented organisational data on job rotation practices. The study revealed that job rotation at Zamtel was implemented inconsistently across departments and that there were limited standardized guidelines or monitoring mechanisms. As a result, the researcher had to rely heavily on participant narratives and departmental experiences. This limitation reinforces the recommendation that Zamtel should develop standardized job rotation guidelines and strengthen its performance management and monitoring systems to ensure consistency in implementation.

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